

Toward New Space **ESD-resistant** **antistatic cables**

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NEW SMART ANTISTATIC MATERIAL & LOW VOLTAGE INSULATED WIRES

→ NEW SPECIAL
BULK RESISTIVITY RANGE:
 $\rho \approx [10^8 - 10^{14}] \text{ ohm.cm}$

- Insulative at Operative Voltage (<100V)
- ANTISTATIC if voltage increase (anomaly)

Project objectives and context

- Development of Space **ESD-resistant antistatic Cables and insulations materials** for Space applications

Two related recent **ESA** projects:

- ❖ RFQ/3-14156/14/NL/BW) (**LIST + Axon'**)
→ **Result presented by Dr Addiego (LIST) at 3rd SPCD (2018)**
- ❖ ITT AO/1-7877/14/NL/RA (**Axon'**)
→ **This presentation**

Followed at ESA by: Denis Lacombe & Léo Farhat

ElectroStatic Discharge (ESD) risks in Space

ESD RISK IN SPACE

Radiation environment

Particles energy and fluxes

Charge build-up in insulations

ESD/Arcing risk

MAIN REASON:

→ Too good insulations materials!

- Ex: Electrons trapped inside the dielectrics
- Risk function of Materials electrical properties, Particles Flux & Energy at the specific localization, ...

(Image Credits: ESA)

ESD Risks Mitigation Strategies

HOW TO PREVENT WIRE INSULATION CHARGING ?

- Increase shielding thickness
- Add conductive layers

→ Add weight & complexity (grounding, termination, bonding,..)

- Use “leaky” dielectrics

Modified « Antistatic » Insulation
This ESA Project Target

- Mass saving
- Flexibility / easy to use
- No grounding required

Antistatic insulation concept

Electrical classification of insulation materials

Concept :

→ **Control of the charge decay rate** through the insulation

How?

→ **Modified insulation for specific volume resistivity**

Requirements

Based on **Spacecraft charging Standards:**

- ESA ECSS-E-ST-20-06C*
- NASA-HDBK-4002*
- JAXA-JERG-2-211A*

TARGET RANGE

Insulative
Standard Space insulations
 $\rho \geq 10^{17}$ ohm.cm

Antistatic

Static-Dissipative

Moderate Conductive

Conductive

Innovative ESD-resistant wires concept

Standard insulation
(high volume resistivity)

Trapped electrons

Wire insulation

conductor

- Dielectric Charging Risk
- Insulation Voltage increase
- Risk of Arcing / Breakdown

New Concept
for mass saving,
easy integration,
and flexibility

→ **Control** of the electrical **charge decay rate** through the **insulation** to nearest conductor

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R&D - Study of the Influence of....

- ✓ materials nature & formulations
- ✓ manufacturing parameters
- ✓ re-processing stages and methods
- ✓ measurements methods
- ✓ temperature (-200°C +160°C)
- ✓ material thickness & structure

...

→ ...on Materials & Wires Properties:

- Volume Resistivity / Insulation resistance
- Breakdown voltage / Dielectric Strength
- Tensile and elongation at break, E modulus
- Abrasion, cut-through, shrinkage, ...

ESA AO/1-7877/14/NL/RA -

Standard influence of:

- ✓ material
- ✓ manufact
- ✓ reproc
- ✓ measu
- ✓ tempe
- ✓ material thickness & st

...AFTER FEW YEARS OF RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT...

→ Materials & Finished Wires Properties

- Volume Resistivity / Insulation resistance
- Breakdown voltage / Dielectric Strength
- Tensile and elongation at break, E modulus
- Abrasion, cut-through, shrinkage, ...

Main Results

ESD-type classification of insulation materials

ESA ECSS-E-ST-20-06C

Project main objective = Success!

**NEW RANGE OF
« ANTISTATIC » WIRES
PROTOTYPES WITH
 $\rho \approx [10^8 - 10^{14}] \text{ ohm.cm}$**

Wires designs similar to **ESCC 3901/012 style** :

- ✓ PASS all mechanical requirements
- ✓ PASS cold bend and thermal ageing tests at 230°C
- ✓ PASS voltages tests at 500Vdc

Results examples – Focus:

STABLE ELECTRICAL PROPERTIES between at least $[-80^{\circ}\text{C}^*$ to $+160^{\circ}\text{C}$
 * + similar result immersed at -200°C

“SMART” ANTISTATIC BEHAVIOR
 → Apparent Volume resistivity function of differential Voltage
 → “Smart” Dynamic Charge decay rate : **Reach Antistatic range if voltage >100V (Reversible)**

Smart Antistatic Wire : W4825M1

Main conclusions

→ **Project Success** : New **antistatic wires** prototypes developed in target range ($\rho \approx 10^8 - 10^{14}$ ohm.cm)

- Compliant with **low voltage Space systems** (at least 100V)
- Mechanical and thermal performances similar to Standard qualified ETFE insulated wires (ESCC3901/012)
- **Low mass, easy to use, no grounding required** compared to alternative solutions (additional shielding, conductive layers...)

This ESA ITT Objective and Result

Perspectives

→ Axon' Antistatic wires prototypes available to Space users

- Further testing/development required for higher TRL target
 - **Investigation of Charging parameters of these new wires and materials** to ensure Space functionality? (example: ONERA SIRENE facility = Thermal Cycling in vacuum + GEO like spectra irradiation)?
 - Influence of **Total Ionizing dose up to X?** (tested up to 30MRad - OK)
 - **Harmonized Space-users requirements** update – for a complete ESCC3901-style qualification – cable design/materials adjustments

This ESA ITT Objective and Result

Next Target?

Image credit ESA

Thanks for your Toward New Space **ESD-resistant antistatic cables** attention!

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